

Colon cancer championship phase V4

ID: c3d944ee-45ef-47a5-8968-8ab0673646bf

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/c3d944ee-45ef-47a5-8968-8ab0673646bf/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 692

Subjects count: 679

Age range: Between 33 years and 94 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): ABDOMEN, CHEST, BRAIN, NECK, LUNG, WHOLEBODY, EXTREMITY, AORTA, TORAX, CAP, Unknown

Modality: CT, CR